

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH AMIDES.
PART XV. OF 6-BROMOPIPERONAL

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6-Bromopiperonal has been condensed with amides; the condensation went fairly well with acetamide, propionamide and *n*-heptamide, giving 6-bromopiperonal-bisamides. It gave about 67% yield of the corresponding biuret with urea. The yield from the condensation with benzamide was poor, and that from formamide was nil. Different conditions have been specified.

6-Bromopiperonal has been condensed with several amides. On the whole the yields were much less than those obtained from the condensations with amides of piperonal and of 6-nitropiperonal (Pandya and Varghese, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 14A, 18, 25). This is almost a contrast with the 6-bromopiperonal-maleic acid condensation, where the yield was excellent (Pandya, Miss Pandya and Sethi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, in the press). The products were all of the bisamide type. The main difficulty was the very easy volatility of 6-bromopiperonal, so that reactions in the dry state without a solvent did not proceed, the aldehyde soon subliming away to the top of the flask. Different solvents or condensing agents were found useful, such as pyridine, acetic acid or pyridine acetate, the highest yield coming from one or the other in the case of different amides. Pyridine was ineffective except in the cases of *n*-heptamide and of urea, which in the presence of pyridine gave the highest yields of 36% and 67% respectively. The yields from acetamide and propionamide were the next best, being 29% and 23% respectively. Benzamide gave a very poor yield of about 4% and formamide did not seem to condense at all, neither did piperonal or 6-nitropiperonal condense with formamide.

Temperature was a very important factor. No condensation took place on the water-bath; the optimum temperature was found to be 105°-110°, and the time of the heating varied from 8 hours to nearly 15 hours.

All the products obtained are white, needle-shaped crystals, melting above or very slightly below 200°. They are insoluble in water or in the usual organic solvents, except alcohol, which could be used for recrystallisation. They do not react with Baeyer's reagent or bromine water in the cold.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation with Benzamide.—The easy sublimibility of the 6-bromopiperonal was the main difficulty for which no condensation product could be obtained in some of the earlier experiments. Heating alone on a water-bath (2 hours), heating at 105-110° (2 hours), heating with pyridine (1:2:1.5 mol.) at 105-110° for 14 hours, heating at 120-130° for 3 hours with pyridine, and with absolute alcohol (water-bath) for 14 hours, at 105-110° for 15 hours with pyridine (3 mols. and 6 mols.), all these failed to give any product, the reactants being recovered unchanged for the most part.

Heating with pyridine acetate (aldehyde 1.2 g., amide 1.2 g., pyridine 3 drops and glacial acetic acid 1 c. c., 1:2:0.1:3.5 mol. nearly) at 105-110° for 14 hours gave a small

amount of a product, which, treated in the usual way, melted (crude) at 210° (higher than the melting points of the aldehyde or of the amide).

Another experiment with the same amounts of the aldehyde and the amide and 2 c. c. of glacial acetic acid (1:2:7 mol.) and heating at $105-110^{\circ}$ for 15 hours gave 0.1 g. of a product, melting at 227° . It came out in fine, silky white needles (hot alcohol). A second experiment was repeated with double the quantities of each and gave 0.2 g. of the same, the yield being 4.4% of theory (as bisbenzamide). It was almost insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. It did not affect in the cold Baeyer's reagent, bromine water or bromine in chloroform solution. It gave a yellow colour with cold concentrated sulphuric acid; but when water was added, a light violet coloured ring developed at the junction of the two layers which turned brown on shaking. (Found: Br 17.24. 6-Bromopiperonyl-bisbenzamide, $C_{22}H_{17}O_4N_2$ Br, requires Br, 17.66 per cent).

Condensation with Acetamide.—When the aldehyde and acetamide were heated alone (1:4 mol.) on a water-bath or at $105-110^{\circ}$, in two hours the aldehyde had all sublimed. Some product was obtained with pyridine acetate (aldehyde 1.2 g., acetamide 1.2 g., pyridine 0.2 g. and glacial acetic acid 0.5 c. c., i. e. 1:4:0.5:1.75 mol.) at $105-110^{\circ}$ and on 12 hours' heating. The crude product (0.6 g.) was obtained in the usual way, melting at 225° and at 230° after purification. The yield was 0.4 g. (23% of theory of the bisacetamide). A second experiment, with double the quantities, gave 1 g. yield (29% of theory). With pyridine alone (1:4:1 mol.) the yield was very small.

Its properties were similar to those described for the bisbenzamide. Cold concentrated sulphuric acid gave a light yellow colour; addition of water produced a violet ring, and shaking gave a pinkish brown colour. (Found: Br, 23.84. 6-Bromopiperonyl-bisacetamide, $C_{19}H_{15}O_4N_2$ Br, requires Br, 24.31 per cent).

Condensation with Propionamide.—There was no condensation when the aldehyde and propionamide (1:2) were heated alone on a water-bath or at $105-110^{\circ}$. With glacial acetic acid (1:2:1.75 mol.) and on heating at $105-110^{\circ}$ for 9 hours about 0.6 g. of a product melting at 213° was obtained. Recrystallisations (hot alcohol, twice) raised the melting point to 225° which did not rise further. The yield was 0.4 g. (23% of theory). In the presence of pyridine alone (1:2:1 mol.) and heating at $105-110^{\circ}$ for 9 hours gave only about 3% yield. Heating for 16 hours with glacial acetic acid (1:1:3.5 mol.) gave again a 23% yield. Heating at $110-115^{\circ}$ raised the yield to 32%. White, needle-shaped crystals (hot alcohol) melting at 225° had the same properties as have been described for the bisbenzamide. (Found: Br, 21.93. 6-Bromopiperonyl-bispropionamide, $C_{14}H_{17}O_4N_2$ Br, requires Br, 22.41 per cent).

Condensation with n-Heptamide.—Heating the two alone was again found to be useless. Heating with glacial acetic acid (1:2:3.5 mol.) on a water-bath for 13 hours also gave negative result. The flask was then heated at $105-110^{\circ}$ for another 15 hours. The crude product was washed with chloroform (which dissolved both the amide and the aldehyde), then several times with warm water and then with ether; this gave a crude product melting at 181° and at 183° after recrystallisation; yield 0.8 g. (36% of theory). The same substance in the same yield was obtained when the condensation was carried out in the presence of pyridine (1:2:1 mol.) on a water-bath for 3 hours, and then at $105-110^{\circ}$ for 15 hours. Larger amounts of glacial acetic acid (1:2:7 mols.) did not augment the

yield (which was only 22%). The properties of the bis-*n*-heptamide were similar to those described above. (Found: Br, 16.69. 6-Bromopiperonyl-bis-*n*-heptamide, $C_{22}H_{33}O_4N_2Br$, requires Br, 17.06 per cent).

Condensation with Urea.—As usual, heating the two alone (aldehyde, 1.2 g. and urea, 0.6 g., 1:2 mol.) on a water-bath for 3 hours, made all the aldehyde sublime away without any condensation having taken place. Heating at 105-110° for 8 hours, however, had the desired effect. The mass melted and resolidified. By extracting with water and chloroform and filtering, a brownish product was obtained, which after purification melted at 198-99°, yield 1.15 g. It had the usual properties, given above, of the bisamides. (Found: Br, 25.02. 6-Bromopiperonyl-biuret, $C_{10}H_8O_4N_2Br$, requires Br, 25.48 per cent; 6-bromopiperonyldiurea, $C_{10}H_{11}O_4N_4Br$, requires Br, 23.46 per cent).

TABLE I
Maximum yields

Amide.	Piperonal.	6-Nitropiperonal.	6-Bromopiperonal.
Formamide	Nil	Nil	Nil
Acetamide	42%	61%	29%
Propionamide	36	15	23
<i>n</i> -Heptamide	77	55	36
Benzamide	64	25	4
Cinnammamide	82	82	Not tried
Urea	Not tried	Not tried	67

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